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SHORT NOTES / BREVI NOTE

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FEEDING OF BLUE ROCK THRUSH *MONTICOLA SOLITARIUS* CHICKS FROM HATCHING TO FLEDGING

Alimentazione dei pulcini di Passero solitario Monticola solitarius dalla schiusa all'involo

INTRODUCTION

The Blue Rock Thrush *Monticola solitarius* is a common breeding resident in the Maltese Islands, present on all the larger islands as well as some of the smaller ones such as Fungus Rock (SULTANA *et al.*, 2011). Locally, this species has always been associated with sea-cliffs and deep rocky valleys where it builds the nest in cracks and cavities in the cliff faces. By the latter part of the 20th Century, it started nesting in fortification walls, stone quarry walls and disused or derelict buildings in remote areas among others, it has also been known to nest in church steeples or domes and more recently inside inhabited buildings (SCHEMBRI, 1843; WRIGHT, 1864; DESPOTT, 1917; SULTANA *et al.*, 1975, 2011). The nest may be as high as 120m, as on the sea cliffs at Ta' Ċenċ, or as low as 2-3m above ground. ROBERTS (1954) recorded a nest in a moat, and therefore actually below normal ground level.

The untidy nest is rather bulky and flat, with a shallow cup. Both sexes take part in nest building, using fine roots, dry grasses and small twigs. If the pair is using the same site used in the previous year, they may simply reconstruct the old nest. Blue Rock Thrushes often keep to the same site for a number of years; a pair at Il-Harrâx even had two sites, which they used alternately for several years (SULTANA *et al.*, 2011). The pair at the National Museum of Natural History, Mdina alternatively uses two sites in the same building in the same season. Two to six eggs (usually 3-5) are laid from late March, although DESPOTT (1916) gave a range of 5-7 eggs, with six as the normal clutch size. The colour is pale blue with varying amounts of fine reddish spots which are occasionally lacking. Incubation takes about 15 days and is carried out mainly by the female, during which time the male stays in the vicinity, and may step in when the female is away feeding. The male often utters its anxiety calls at anyone's approach.

Diet mainly consists of invertebrates (mostly large insects and snails), small reptiles and fruit. The bird feeds on the ground and frequently pounces on its prey from a perching post, but it also takes insects on the wing (SULTANA & GAUCI, 1980; FALZON, 1988). One male near Ghadira Nature Reserve (in spring-summer 2002) was often seen visiting Spanish Sparrow nests, possibly taking newly hatched young (SULTANA *et al.*, 2011).

Both parents feed the young, the food consisting mainly of caterpillars (Lepidoptera), small sized Hymenoptera, Orthoptera, other insects, both sparrow species chicks (*Passer hispaniolensis*

and *P. montanus*), wall lizards *Podarcis filfolensis*, geckoes *Tarentola mauritanica* and *Hemidactylus turcicus*, with prey-size increasing according to the chick's age. Some birds catch their prey from the immediate vicinity of the nest site while others fly a considerable distance in search of food. The young fledge after about 15 days but are still fed by the parents for a few more days (SULTANA, 1978, 2002; SULTANA & GAUCI, 1970, 1982; SULTANA *et al.*, 2011).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This study was conducted at the National Museum of Natural History, Vilhena Palace in the old Capital city of Mdina, over an eight-year period from 2016 to 2023. A prospecting pair was first noted in 2015 where they observed regularly between May and July, but in autumn and winter, only the male remained in the area. In the following year they nested successfully inside the inner courtyard of the Palace. Two nesting sites were regularly used, alternating between the first and second brood. One nest was built on a narrow ledge inside the building next to an open courtyard at a height of 6.78 mt above ground, and the second nest was constructed inside a hole in the fortification walls within the building, facing South-Southwest at 3.3 meters above roof level. Normally, two broods are raised annually, except for 2016, 2021 and 2022 when only a single brood was produced. In 2022, egg laying took place almost a month later than usual and so this may have resulted in only one brood being raised, with the young fledging in the first week of June. No attempts to lay a second brood were observed in 2022. A total of forty-three (43) chicks fledged from 2016 to 2023, twelve of which were found dead on the premises (Table 1). Mortality causes varied from predation by domestic cats and a at least 1.5 mt long Western Whipsnake *Hierophis carbonarius*, to starvation as a result of becoming trapped in shafts or other confined spaces and later found long dead. As both nests were out of reach, the ringing of chicks had to be carried out once the chicks left the nest. The fledged birds were caught by hand and ringed early in the morning when they “jump” from the nest and are found in the museum's corridors or courtyard.

In the last two decades an expansion of the bird's breeding territory has been observed, with more birds present in urban areas (SULTANA *et al.*, 2011; EPSILON MALTA, 2019). In 2022, no less than four pairs were observed in the Rabat/Mdina area, and these increased to six pairs in 2023.

Table 1. Number of hatched and fledged chicks from Vilhena Palace (2016-2023)

Year	No. Fledged	No. survived
2016	3 (1 brood)	1
2017	8 (2 broods)	6
2018	7 (2 broods)	5
2019	6 (2 broods)	4
2020	8 (2 broods)	5
2021	2 (1 brood)	1
2022	3 (1 brood)	3
2023	6 (2 broods)	4

The data for this study was collected through direct observations, photographs taken with a Canon 7D camera with a 100x400mm lens, as well as by means of video recording using a Sony HandyCam. Images were used to record the adult movements and in the identification of the prey

presented to the chicks. The video-camera was set opposite a favorite stopping perch used by both parents before flying up to the nest. The video camera was switched on from one hour before sunrise to 30 minutes after sunset during the chick rearing stage. Footage was recorded and stored on a laptop.

RESULTS

The food items identified from direct observations as well as from digitized media as presented to the chicks was as follows.

In the first two days from hatching, both parents presented tiny prey items, mainly small larvae and adults of various Coleoptera and Hymenopteran species, ranging in size from 1 to 3 cm long. In the following four days, food consisted mainly of caterpillars (Lepidoptera), ranging in size from 4 to 6 cm long with occasional larger beetles being fed. The following eight days, the main food source were Spanish Sparrow *Passer hispaniolensis* and Tree Sparrow *Passer montanus* chicks taken from nearby nests. Both sparrows nest inside and outside the palace walls. Towards the latter week before fledging, reptiles formed the main diet with both species of Geckoes *Tarentula mauritanica* and *Hemidactylus turcicus*, Maltese Wall Lizard *Podarcis filfolensis* and Ocellated Skink *Chalcides ocellatus* all being fed to the growing chicks (Table 2).

Table 2. Prey type offered to chicks in nest from hatching to fledging.

Prey	Days from hatching to fledging x = day of hatching														
	x+1	x+2	x+3	x+4	x+5	x+6	x+7	x+8	x+9	x+10	x+11	x+12	x+13	x+14	x+15
Coleoptera/Hymenoptera	■	■	■	■											
Caterpillars 1-3 cm long	■	■	■	■	■										
Caterpillars 4-6 cm long			■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■		
Chicks of <i>Passer montanus</i> and <i>P. hispaniolensis</i>						■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
<i>Tarentula mauritanica</i> , <i>Hemidactylus turcicus</i>									■	■	■	■	■	■	■
<i>Podarcis filfolensis</i>										■	■	■	■	■	■
<i>Chalcides ocellatus</i>												■	■	■	■

CONCLUSION

This study focused on one pair of Blue Rock Thrushes, nesting in a sub-urban area inside a building frequented by people on a daily basis. The Palace houses the National Museum of Natural History as well as the offices of the Mdina Local Council. Over the years, the adults became accustomed to continuous human presence close to the nesting site. But, during the chick rearing stage, the adult's behavior is like those birds nesting on sea-cliffs and other inaccessible areas, with the

adults continuously uttering the characteristic alarm call and hiding behind protruding stone features. Future studies will focus on the level of tolerance (human presence) the adult birds can withstand during the breeding season. Comparative research is required, particularly from other areas on dietary requirements from rural and sub-urban areas as well as fledging success. It is also interesting to identify and confirm the triggers for the recent expansion of the Blue Rock Thrush to move away from traditional areas and occupy non-coastal sub-urban and urban breeding sites.

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